

Appraisal Approach to Design for Emotion

Pieter M.A. Desmet*

** Department of Industrial Design, Delft University of Technology, Delft, the Netherlands,
p.m.a.desmet@tudelft.nl*

Abstract: This paper introduces an approach to emotion driven design that was based on the process that underlies emotional responses to consumer products. Three levels, and nine associated classes of product-evoked emotions are discussed, which are each the outcome of a unique pattern of eliciting conditions. The approach is based on two main propositions. The first is that all emotional reactions result from an appraisal process in which the individual appraises the product as (potentially) harming or favoring his or her wellbeing. The second is that products can generate at least three classes of emotional stimuli: stimuli with a product-focus; with an activity-focus, and with a self-focus. The appraisals and three levels of person-product relationships combine to a framework of nine sources of product emotions. The framework is used as the basis for an approach to design that aims for three levels of emotional product appeal.

Key words: *Emotion, Appraisal, Design Approach.*

1. Introduction

The heart of emotion – in all of its multifaceted manifestations – is that we feel good or we feel bad [1]. This applies as much to the emotions towards products as to those we experience in social encounters: products elicit feelings that are good and/or feelings that are bad. Evidently, we generally want to design products that elicit good or pleasant feelings – not feelings that are bad or unpleasant. Good feelings have all kinds of likable effects: products that feel good, are bought, are bought a second time, are talked about in a positive way, contribute to brand image, and are forgiven for design imperfections. Bad feelings, vice versa, generate disappointed users, complaints, brand damage, shrinking sales. The current paper discusses a framework that represents a psychological view on product emotion because it is based on the cognitive mechanisms that intervene between seeing, using, owning, or thinking about a product, and the emotional outcome. The first part of the paper discusses some key insights in human emotions; in the second, the link between emotions and product design is made; the third formulates some initial ideas for a practical approach to emotion-driven design.

2. Three Main Emotional Appraisals

Emotions arise in response to events that are important to the well-being of the individual. The individual therefore has to grasp this importance in some way; he or she has to appraise the event's relevance for their wellbeing [2]. Appraisal is (in this context) a nonconscious sense-evaluation that 'diagnoses' whether an event has adaptational relevance to the individual [3]. Often, three main appraisals types are distinguished [1]: a usefulness appraisal (the extent to which an event supports or obstructs me in reaching my goals), a pleasantness appraisal (the extent to which an event provides pleasantness or pain), and a rightfulness appraisal (the extent to

which an event meets or exceeds my standards or expectations). These appraisals, which we consider the three main forces that drive emotional experience and behavior, can manifest in a wide variety of valuations; see Figure 1 for some examples.

Figure 1. examples of positive and negative manifestations of three key appraisal types.

Positive usefulness appraisals value the situation as helpful, purposeful, advantageous, or beneficial, whereas negative usefulness appraisals value the situation as harmful, disadvantageous, obstructive or ineffective. Positive pleasantness appraisals value the situation as delightful, lovely, beautiful, or charming, whereas negative pleasantness appraisals value the situation as appalling, unattractive, dull, or unattractive. Positive rightfulness appraisals value the situation as fair, legitimate, legal, or sensible, and negative rightfulness appraisals value situations as unfair, wrong, unreasonable, or intolerable. These key appraisals are universal emotional forces that hide behind all human emotions. Every perceived change is appraised in terms of: is it useful, is it pleasurable, and is it rightful? A situation can thus elicit a good feeling because it is useful, because it is pleasurable, or because it is rightful. Vice versa, a situation can elicit a bad feeling because it is harmful, because it is painful, or because it is wrongful. This applies to all of our relationships – with things, with people, with situations, thoughts, the world in general, and ourselves.

3. Situational Meaning of Products

We can appraise a product as delightful, and desire to own it, as useless and wanting to dispose of it, as ugly and wanting to hide it in a closet. The main clue of the process of emotion is that it motivates us to engage in and strengthen relationships that support our wellbeing, and to weaken or terminate relationships that endanger our wellbeing. Examples of emotional tendencies are to touch or taste a product, to buy, to turn away from, discard, approach, reject, to examine, to stop using the product, to retry interactions, to use more force, or to yell at the product. With respect to products there are (at least) three levels of relationships that are affected by product design [4]: relationship with the product (product focus), with the activity that is facilitated or enabled by product usage (activity focus), and with the life in general (self focus). Firstly (product focus), products are objects that we perceive – see touch, taste, hear, and feel, and because perceiving something is an event in itself, products can elicit emotions ‘as such.’ The emotional impact of a product depends on its material qualities, purposes, meanings, expressions, and on what it does or fails to do. For example, the TV does not respond to the remote

control, the oven starts to produce a scent of freshly baked cookies, the alarm clock sets off, a drawer runs unexpectedly smooth, some signal light starts to blink on the car dashboard, and so on. Note that that this context of experience includes not only those emotions we experience in response to actually perceiving a product, but also in response to thinking of a product, of hearing about a product. Secondly (activity focus), products are used to enable or facilitate all kinds of activities. Products are instruments that are used to ‘get something done’ in some situation: activities that can be useful (e.g. organizing my documents), pleasurable (e.g. ice-skating with friends), or rightful (e.g. washing the car). Individuals will respond emotionally to these activities because they have concerns related to the activities. The emotion is not directed to the product, but the product does play a role because it enables the individual to engage in the activity that evokes the emotion. Examples are: I am excited by making a hiking trip in the snow (which is facilitated by my warm coat); I enjoy talking to my friends (which is facilitated by my mobile phone). Thirdly (self focus), owning and using products have an influence on one’s identity; they affect an individual’s self-perception and how they are perceived by others. An expensive buggy enables someone be a good parent, crayons enable someone to be creative, and an SUV car makes someone look irresponsible. People are emotional about who they are and how others perceive them, and thus also about the effects of products on their identity. Examples are: I feel awkward because I have to use crutches; I feel secure when wearing a fashionable new suit.

4. Emotion Driven Design

In line with the three levels of human-product interactions, we propose that there are three levels of emotional appeal: an object appeal (the degree to which the product is appealing), an activity appeal (the degree to which the activity I am engaged in is appealing), and a self appeal (the degree to which I am, or my life is, appealing). In this context, the word ‘appealing’ is used for stimuli that correspond with the three basic human forces: usefulness, pleasantness, and rightfulness. In emotion driven design we can aim for establishing these three levels of appeal. On the basis of this proposition, four steps in design for emotion are formulated:

Step 1: design theme. Identify the product (functionality), the user group, and the situation in which the design will be used. The theme is defined in terms of a user group engaged in an activity in some situation. Examples are: policemen using a communication device when at work in the neighborhood, or caretakers using a bottle when feeding a toddler at home.

Step 2: concern profile. Formulate a concern profile to represent the intended user. This profile is considered to be the point of reference in the users’ appraisals. Because the amount of concerns is infinite in any given situation, the challenge not to aim for completeness, but for a concise profile that is both relevant and inspiring. The profile includes general life concerns, concerns in the usage situation, and concerns given the product design. Key questions helpful in selecting general life concerns are: what do the users expect from themselves in life? What are the standards that they want to live up to? What are their general life goals and aspirations they pursue? What are the experiences and activities they enjoy? Examples are: I should be fit, I want to be autonomous, and I like listening to music in my garden. Key questions in formulating concerns given the situation, are: what do the users expect from themselves in the usage situation; what are their usage standards? What do they want to accomplish in the usage situation; what are their goals? What are the activities and interactions they enjoy in the usage situation; what are their usage sensitivities? Examples are: I should be patient

with my clients at work, I want my son to enjoy himself at school, and I like encouraging interactions. Key questions in formulating concerns given the product design are: what are the users' expectations and standards about the product? What kind of object properties do they enjoy? What do they want to accomplish with the product? Examples are: A remote control phone should be strong enough not to break when I drop it, I like my table to be made of honest materials, and I want to be able to use my phone when it is raining.

Step 3: product profile. The third step is to create a product profile that represent the designer's vision on how to align with the concern profile – specifying three qualities: the product's significance, intentions, and character. Significance represents the key consequences that we want to design for; e.g., I have many friends, I am relaxed, my baby is happy, or I am inspired. The intentions of the product are defined by the purpose it will be designed to have, such as, the product enables me to talk freely, enables me to meet people, to be spontaneous, or to be at work on time, and the interaction personality with which intends to fulfill this purpose; such as, the product stimulates me, invites me, seduces me, or forces me. The character represents the product's appearance, such as, the product is sexy, rough, delicate, natural, or colorful. The product profile is used to formulate a product statement. Some examples are: a delicate product that enables me to have a relaxed life by seducing me to talk freely. A tough product that enables me to have many friends by forcing me to open up to others. The concern profile and product profile can be used as a reference in all stages of the design process in order to safeguard the emotional fittingness of the final design.

Step 4: product design. The fourth step is to design a product that fits with the product statement.

5. Discussion

The next step will be to make it more explicit by means of explorative design applications, and to explore application opportunities in other domains than product design, such as, service and interaction design. The main contribution is that it enables the design team to formulate a mutual design vision with respect to the emotional impact of the design. Although it does not objectify this process, it does offer some steps that facilitate the communication between team members and with the client. In addition, in the design case, it was found helpful in ensuring that emotion was considered at the start of the project, and in enabling the design team to illustrate the layered nature of product emotions to the client, stressing that the emotional impact is not only determined by appearance, but also by the significance of the concept and the intentions of the interactions.

6. References

- [1] Ortony, A., Clore, G. L. and Collins, A. (1988). The cognitive structure of emotions. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [2] Frijda, N. H. (1986). The emotions. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [3] Lazarus, R. S. (1991). Emotion and adaptation. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [4] Desmet, P. M. A. (2008). Product Emotion. In: H. N. J. Schifferstein and P. Hekkert (Eds). Product experience (pp. 379-397). Amsterdam: Elsevier.